

Naphthoquinones of *Plumbago* Species : A ReviewB. DINDA^a, A. K. HAJRA^a and G. CHEL^b^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Life Sciences, Tripura University, Agartala-799 004

Manuscript received 16 October 1997

A brief review on the naphthoquinones and their analogs isolated from different *Plumbago* species (Plumbaginaceae) is presented. An up-to-date list of naphthoquinones and their analogs isolated from these plants along with their physical constants and spectral data, method of isolation, structure elucidation, synthetic studies, chemical transformations, biogenetic studies, and biological activities are discussed.

India has a long tradition for the use of plant products in the field of Ayurvedic, Unani, and Homoeopathic systems of medicine. Versatile medicinal uses of *Plumbago* species have been known in India since the time of *Caraka* and *Susruta*¹⁻³ and elsewhere in the world⁴⁻⁶. The genus *Plumbago* consists of about 10 species⁷, namely, *P. auriculata* (syn. *P. capensis*) (P₁), *P. coerulea* (P₂), *P. europea* (P₃), *P. pearsonii* (syn. *P. siffruticosa*) (P₄), *P. pulchella* (P₅), *P. rosea* (syn. *P. indica*, *P. coccinea*) (P₆), *P. scandens* (P₇), *P. tristis* (syn. *P. vogeliaefolia*) (P₈), *P. wissii* (P₉) and *P. zeylanica* (syn. *P. viscosa*) (P₁₀). Three species P₁, P₆ and P₁₀ are available in India, five in Africa^{7,8} and seven in U.K.⁹.

Among the ten species, only P₁₀ is grown widely in tropical and subtropical regions of Asia, Australia and Africa, and hence more extensive studies on this species have been done. The most common variety P₁₀ is well-known as *Chita* in Bengali and Hindi. Morphologically, P₆ is distinctive with red petals and P₁ with blue petals, while the others have white petals.

Although Thomson reported the naturally occurring naphthoquinones in his monographs¹⁰⁻¹², no comprehensive review article on the chemistry of naphthoquinones of the genus *Plumbago* has appeared so far. It encouraged us to prepare this review article. An up-to-date list of naphthoquinones and its analogs isolated from the leaf, root and aerial parts of different *Plumbago* species is given :

(A) Monomers :

Plumbagin (1) : P₁, P₂, P₅, P₇⁹; P₃^{13,56}; P₄⁶⁸; P₆^{9,5,17}; P₁₀^{9,14,16,17,69}. 3-Chloroplumbagin (2) : P₁₀¹⁶. Droserone (3) : P₆²⁰; P₁₀^{18,19}. 2-Methylnaphthazarin (4) : P₁₀²¹. 6-Hydroxyplumbagin (5) : P₆²³. Isoshinanolone (6) : P₁₀¹⁸. *epi*-Isoshinanolone (7) : P₇²⁵. Dihydrodroserone (pz-5) (8) : P₁₀²⁶.

(B) Dimers :

3,3'-Biplumbagin (9) : P₁₀¹⁶. Elliptinone (6,6'-Biplumbagin) (10) : P₆²⁰. Chitranone (3,6'-biplumbagin) (11) : P₁₀²¹. Isozeylanone (13) : P₁₀²⁰. Tetrahydro-3,3'-biplumbagin (17) : P₁₀¹⁸. Chitanone (18) : P₁₀²⁹.

(C) Trimer :

Plumbazeylanone (19) : P₁₀⁵⁰.

The molecular formulae, mass spectrally derived molecu-

- 1; R¹=R²=H (Plumbagin) 10; R=6-Plumbaginylyl, R¹=H
 2; R¹=Cl, R²=H 11; R=3-Plumbaginylyl; R¹=H
 3; R¹=OH, R²=H 12; R=H, R¹=8-plumbaginylyl
 4; R¹=H, R²=OH
 5; 1, C(6)-OH
 8; 3,2,3-Dihydro, C(2)-β-Me, C(3)-α(OH)

- 6; C(1)-α-OH
 7; C(1)-β-OH

lar weights (within parentheses), m.ps. (°C) and uv absorption maxima (nm) in ethanol, unless otherwise stated (with log ε values within parentheses) of these naphthoquinones are as follows :

1 : C₁₁H₈O₃ (188); 78°; λ_{max} 210 (4.53), 255sh (4.07), 267 (4.08) (Band II), 424 nm (3.67) (Band I). 2 : C₁₁H₇O₃Cl (222); 125-26°; λ_{max} 215 (4.49), 249 (3.92), 282 (4.11), 431 (3.60). 3 : C₁₁H₈O₄ (204); 181°; λ_{max} 228 (4.62), 278 (4.52), 400 (3.66). 4 : C₁₁H₈O₄ (204); 174-75°; λ_{max} 214 (4.50), 280 (3.92), 478 (3.69), 508 (3.72), 544 (3.50). 5 : C₁₁H₈O₄ (204); 134-35°; λ_{max} 215 (3.60), 274 (3.32), 488 (2.89), 5.10sh (2.87), 545sh (2.66). 6 : C₁₁H₁₂O₃ (192); 160° (dec); λ_{max} 217 (4.52), 259 (4.09), 335 (3.76). 7 : C₁₁H₁₂O₃ (192); 90°; λ_{max} 260 (4.03), 334 (3.56). 8 : C₁₁H₁₀O₄ (206); 67°; λ_{max} 212 (4.42), 260 (4.03), 338 (3.71). 9 : C₂₂H₁₄O₆ (374); 214-16°; λ_{max} 215 (4.70), 257sh (4.26), 274 (4.28), 413 (3.84). 10 : C₂₂H₁₄O₆ (374); 310° (dec); λ_{max} (CHCl₃) 265 (4.48), 442 (4.09). 11 : C₂₂H₁₄O₆ (374); 118-20°; λ_{max} (dioxane) 257 (4.25), 437 (4.22). 12 : C₂₂H₁₄O₆ (374); 193-95°; λ_{max} 264 (4.42), 436 (3.87). 13 : C₂₂H₁₄O₆ (374); 192-94°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 217, 264, 422. 14 : C₂₂H₁₄O₆ (374);

14; C(2)- β -Me, R= β -H, R¹, R²= Δ 13; R=R²=H, R¹=OH
19; C(2)- α -Me; R= α -Me, R¹=H, 15; R=Me, R¹=H, R²=OH
R²=3-plumbaginyl

16

17; 9, 1,1,2,3-tetrahydro,
C(1)- α -
OH, C(2)- α -Me, C(3)- β -

18

212–14°; λ_{\max} (dioxane) 235 (4.85), 246 (4.72), 350 (4.00), 430 (3.83). 15 : C₂₃H₁₆O₆ (388); 208–10°; λ_{\max} 215 (3.68), 247 (3.80), 275 (3.75), 4.10 (3.44). 16 : C₂₂H₁₆O₇ (416); 83°; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 210 (4.55), 264.5 (4.42), 419.5 (3.91). 17 : C₂₂H₁₈O₆ (378); 109–10°; λ_{\max} 212 (4.70), 263 (4.32), 333 (3.77), 418 (3.63). 18 : C₂₅H₂₄O₆ (420); 90°; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 212 (4.62), 261 (4.22), 334 (3.72), 415 (3.51). 19 : C₃₄H₂₄O₉ (576); 246–48°; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 218 (4.64), 232sh (4.41), 249sh (4.26), 276 (4.18), 354 (3.76), 418 (3.71).

All these naphthoquinones contain, besides aryl protons, mainly methyl, methylene and hydroxyl groups as substituents. The characteristic proton signals of the substituents in their ¹H nmr spectra are as follows.

For substituted naphthoquinone unit in monomers, dimers and trimers: C(2)-CH₃ : δ 1.99–2.30 (d, *J* 1.5 Hz); C(3)-H : δ 6.58–6.89 (s or q, *J* 1.5 Hz); C(5)-OH : δ 11.03–13.23 (br s). For dihydro (8) and tetrahydro naphthoquinone units (6, 7, 17) : C(2)-CH₃ : δ 1.11–1.25 (d, *J* 6/7 Hz); C(1) or C(3)-H : δ 4.44–4.66 (d, *J* 2.5–10 Hz). For bis(naphthoquinonyl)-methanes (13, 15) : CH₂ : δ 3.96 (br s). For condensed bis(naphthoquinones) (14, 19) : CH₂ (in 14) : δ 3.42 and 3.46 (1H, dd each, *J* 6.5, 16.5 Hz); CH₂ (in 19) : δ 2.74 and 3.25 (1H, dd each, *J* 13.3; 13.9 Hz).

The ¹³C nmr data of only two compounds have been

reported. These are : 1 δ 181.5 (C-1), 149.4 (C-2), 135.2 (C-3), 190.0 (C-4), 161.0 (C-5), 123.9 (C-6), 135.9 (C-7), 119.0 (C-8), 131.9 (C-9), 115.0 (C-10), 16.2 (C-11-H₃); 19 δ 184.1, 190.0 (2 \times quinone CO), 183.6, 189.7, 196.3, 202.7 (4 \times keto CO).

Isolation

The quinones are isolated in the usual way from the phenolic parts of petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and methanol extracts of the various plants by column chromatography and preparative tlc, when necessary, over silica gel. Recently, HPLC has been applied³¹ for the separation of naphthoquinones, such as juglone, lawsone and plumbagin from their mixture using Micro Bondapak-CN column. Quinones have characteristic beautiful yellow, orange, red, or violet colored crystals.

Structure elucidation

1,4-Naphthoquinones are known as α -naphthoquinones. The presence of α -naphthoquinonoid chromophore in them is indicated by their characteristic uv-vis spectra. The presence of hydroxyl group in the aromatic ring of the quinones is indicated by a bathochromic shift in band-I of about 50 nm with alkali²⁹. The dihydro- or tetrahydronaphthoquinones show hypsochromic shift of band-I^{18,26}. The presence of *ortho*-dihydroxy grouping in the quinones is indicated by colored chelate formation with boric acid and anhydrous sodium acetate²⁹. The *peri*-hydroxyl grouping in quinones is also indicated by a bathochromic shift in band-I of about 30 nm with aluminium chloride²⁹. In dimeric quinones, a combination of the monomeric units is observed in uv-vis spectra.

The chelated hydroxy- α -naphthoquinones show two characteristic ir bands at ~1660 (unchelated C=O) and ~1625 cm⁻¹ (chelated C=O). The band for hydroxyl group at about 3500 cm⁻¹ is very weak and it appears in the region 3000 cm⁻¹ and thus merges with aromatic C-H stretching frequencies³².

The ¹H nmr spectra of the hydroxy- α -naphthoquinones are diagnostic to ascertain the vinylic methyl and vinylic proton, in addition to aromatic protons, as discussed earlier.

The mass spectra (EI) of substituted naphthoquinones are useful in the location of substituents in the bicyclic system. The characteristic fragmentation patterns of several substituted naphthoquinones are documented^{20,28,20,33,34}.

Syntheses

Various attempts have been made for the synthesis of plumbagin, a major constituent in different *Plumbago* species. The first approach was made by oxidation of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone with Caro's acid, which led to a poor yield of plumbagin (1)³⁵. Later, it was successfully synthe-

sized from *m*-toluoyl chloride via 6-methyl-1-tetralone in an overall low yield³⁶. Thomson synthesized it in 80% overall yield, from 3-carboxymethylthio-2-methyljuglone (20) by hydrogenolysis with Raney nickel, followed by oxidation with H₂O₂ (Scheme 1)³⁷.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) H₂/Raney Ni, (ii) H₂O₂.

Ichihara *et al.*³⁸ made another approach for its synthesis using Diels-Alder reaction of juglone (21) with cyclopentadiene. The resultant adduct (22) on reduction with DIBAL, followed by a sequence of reactions via ketone 23, furnished 1 in good yield (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Reagents : (i) DIBAL, (ii) (OMe)₂CMe₂, TsOH, (iii) CrO₃/Py, (iv) *n*-BuLi/HMPT, (v) MeI, (vi) PhMe, Δ, (vii) FeCl₃.

In another procedure, Wurn *et al.*³⁹ used Kolbe-Schmidt reaction for the synthesis of 1 from 5-methoxy-1-naphthol. The most elegant procedure was adopted by Kubo *et al.*⁴⁰, in which the bis(methoxymethyl) ether (24) was methylated at C-2 by lithiation, followed by use of dimethyl sulphate, and the product (25) was autooxidized to plumbagin methyl ether using salcomine as catalyst and finally demethylated (Scheme 3).

3,3'-Biplumbagin (9) has been synthesized from 1-acetoxy-4-hydroxy-2-methyl-5-methoxynaphthalene derivative (26) by oxidative coupling to 27, followed oxidation to 28 and demethylation⁴¹. In a later procedure, bijuglone (29) was C-methylated with diazomethane and then thermolyzed⁴² (Scheme 4).

Scheme 3. Reagents : (i) LDA, (ii) Me₂SO₄, (iii) salcomine, (iv) AlCl₃/PhNO₂, HCl.

Scheme 4. Reagents : (i) Ag₂O, (ii) MnO₂, (iii) AlCl₃, (iv) CH₂N₂, Δ.

The synthesis of elliptinone (10) was reported starting from 8-chloroplumbagin, which was converted into the naphthol (30). The latter on oxidation with silver oxide, followed by successive reductive acetylation, hydrogenolysis, oxidative demethylation and hydrolysis, yielded 10⁴⁹. In another method, it was obtained by oxidation of diospyrol (31) with Fremy's salt (Scheme 5)²⁷.

Scheme 5. Reagent : Fremy's salt.

The structure of martinone (12) was confirmed by its synthesis from plumbagin (1)⁴⁴.

Chemical transformations

Some chemical transformations have been reviewed in the monograph of Thomson¹². Therefore, only those reactions which have been published thereafter are discussed here.

Plumbagin (1) was converted into methyl ether (32) on treatment with methyl iodide in chloroform in presence of silver oxide. Compound 32 on treatment with diazomethane

at 0° gave benzindazoleione (33), which on refluxing in toluene yielded 2,3-dimethyljuglone methyl ether (34). A solution of 33 in chloroform-methanol mixture on treatment with caustic soda gave 5,5'-dimethoxy-2,2'-dimethyl-3,3'-ethylenedi-1,4-naphthoquinone (35). When a mixture of 32 and 33 in chloroform-methanol mixture was treated with 1M NaOH solution, Michael type addition occurred, resulting

the homogentisate, the polyacetate-malonate and the mevalonate pathways^{46,47}. But feeding experiments with acetate-1-¹⁴C, 2-¹⁴C and malonate-2-¹⁴C in young shoots of *P₃* suggested that plumbagin and its analogs are produced in higher plants via the polyacetate-malonate pathway⁴⁶. Possible biogenetic pathways of dimeric and trimeric quinones from plumbagin (1) have earlier been suggested^{20,28,30}.

Scheme 6. Chemical transformations of 1. Reagents : (i) MeI/Ag₂O, (ii) CH₂N₂/Et₂O, 0°, (iii) toluene-reflux, (iv) CHCl₃-MeOH-NaOH, (v) CHCl₃-MeOH-NaOH, 32, (vi) KCN-H₂SO₄-EtOH, (vii) Me₂Sn or Ph₂Sn/C₆H₆.

dimethyl ether of 15 (36)²¹. Bromination of 1 with bromine in chloroform resulted 3-bromo-, 6-bromo- and 3,8-dibromoplumbagins¹⁷. When a mixture of an alcoholic solution of 1 and a solution of KCN in dil. H₂SO₄ was allowed to keep at room temperature for 3 days, three products, namely, 2-cyano-2,3-dihydropoplumbagin (37), 2-cyano-2,3-dihydro-3,3'-biplumbagin (38) and 2-cyano-2,3,2',3'-tetrahydro-3,3'-biplumbagin (39) were found¹⁷. A solution of 1 in AcOH on refluxing with NaNO₂ for 4 h afforded 6-nitro- and 8-nitropoplumbagins, the former being the major product¹⁷. The organotin(IV) chelates (40) of 1 were prepared by refluxing a solution of 1 in benzene with dimethyl and diphenyl tin (1 : 2)⁴⁵. Some of these reactions are outlined (Scheme 6).

Biogenesis

Regarding the biogenesis of naphthoquinones, it was suggested that in higher plants these metabolites may be formed by four separate pathways, namely, the shikimate,

Biological activities

Biological activities of crude plant extracts of different *Plumbago* species as well as of plumbagin (1) have been studied exhaustively.

Pharmacological activities :

The root extracts of *Plumbago* species have been incorporated in various Indian indigenous drug formulations, namely, Asokarishtam, Dasamularishta, Livosprin, Livomyn, Livokin, etc.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹. Plumbagin (1) showed significant antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* (at 1 µg ml⁻¹), *Candida albicans* (5-10 µg ml⁻¹)⁵², *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*, *S. albus*, *Salmonella dublin*, *S. paratyphi*, *Corn equi* and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (20 µg ml⁻¹), and antifungal activity against *Rhizotricum nigricans*, *Penicillium canadense*, *P. notatum*, *Entomophthora floccosum*, *Metarrhizium nana* (10 µg ml⁻¹) and *Penicillium lilacinum* (10-20 µg ml⁻¹)⁵². 1 also showed effective antileishmanial

effect *in vitro* and *in vivo* against *Leishmania donovani* and *L. mexicana amazonensis*⁵⁴. Plumbagin (1) showed marked anticancer activity against methylcholanthrene induced fibrosarcoma and P₃₈₈ lymphocytic leukaemia in rats at 2 and 4 mg kg⁻¹ body wt. respectively⁵³. 1 was also reported to have diuretic and sudorific⁵⁵, abortifacient⁵⁶, and anticoagulant⁵⁷ activities.

Pesticidal activities :

The petrol extract of P₁₀ was effective against pest *Lipaphis erysimi*⁵⁸. Plumbagin (1) showed significant antifeedent activity against the African army worms, *Spodoptera exempta*⁵⁰, *Acalymma vittata*⁶⁰, *Achaea janata*⁶¹, *Mythimma separata*⁶²; ecdysis inhibitor activity against lepidopterous and hemipterous pests, *Corcyra cephalonica* and *Spilosoma obliqua*⁶¹, *Dysdercus koenigii*⁶⁹, *Heliothis virescens*, *H. zea*, *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Trichoplusia ni*⁶⁴; larval mortality effect against *Culex fatigans*⁶⁵, molluscicidal activity against snail *Biomphalaria glabrata*^{66,67}; and adult sterilant effect against hemipterans, *Dysdercus koenigii* and *D. cingulatus*⁷⁰.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.H.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Project Assistantship.

References

1. P. RAY and H. N. GUPTA, "Caraka Samhitā (A Scientific Synopsis)", Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, 1980.
2. P. RAY, H. N. GUPTA, and M. RAY, "Suśruta Samhitā (A Scientific Synopsis)", Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, 1980.
3. R. N. CHOPRA, I. C. CHOPRA, K. L. HANDA, and L. D. KAPUR, "Chopra's Indigenous Drugs of India", 2nd. ed., U. N. Dhur and Sons, Calcutta, 1958.
4. J. ATTYGALLE, "Sinhalese Materia Medica", M. D. Gunasena, Colombo, 1917, p. 98.
5. J. M. DALZIEL, "The Useful Plants of West Tropical Africa", Crown Agents, London, 1937.
6. J. C. WILLS in "Dictionary of Flowering Plants and Ferns", ed. H. K. AIRY SHAW, 7th. ed., Cambridge University Press, London, 1966.
7. D. B. DEB, "The Flora of Tripura State", Today and Tomorrow, New Delhi, 1983, Vol. 2, p. 184.
8. R. A. DYER, L. E. CODD, and H. B. RYCROFT, "Flora of Southern Africa", Govt. Printer, Republic of South Africa, Pretoria, 1963, Vol. 26.
9. J. B. HARBORNE, *Phytochemistry*, 1967, 6, 1415.
10. R. H. THOMSON, "Naturally Occurring Quinones", Butterworth, London, 1957.
11. R. H. THOMSON, "Naturally Occurring Quinones", Academic, London, 1971.
12. R. H. THOMSON, "Naturally Occurring Quinones", Chapman and Hall, London, 1987.
13. D. De ASTAFORT, *J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1828, 14, 441.
14. P. FLUCKIGER, *Neues Handwörterbuch Chem.*, 1887, 5, 723.
15. W. BETTINCK, *Nieuw. Tijdschr. Pharm. Nederland*, 1888, 21, 1.
16. G. S. SIDHU and A. V. B. SANKARAM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 2385.
17. B. DINDA, G. CHEL, S. SAHA, and A. PATRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, 33, 502.
18. G. M. K. B. GUNAHERATH, A. A. I. GUNATILAKA, M. U. S. SULTANBAWA, and S. BALASUBRAMANIAM, *Phytochemistry*, 1983, 22, 1245.
19. A. V. B. SANKARAM, A. S. RAO, and G. S. SIDHU, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, 15, 237.
20. B. DINDA, S. K. DAS, and A. K. HAJRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, 34, 525.
21. G. M. K. B. GUNAHERATH, A. A. L. GUNATILAKA, and R. H. THOMSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1988, 407.
22. M. A. FERREIRA, M. A. C. COSTA, and A. C. ALVES, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, 11, 2352.
23. B. DINDA and G. CHEL, *Phytochemistry*, 1992, 31, 3652.
24. M. TEZUKA, C. TAKAHASHI, M. KUROYANAGI, M. SATAKE, K. YOSHIHIRA, and S. NATORI, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, 12, 175.
25. J. BHATTACHARYYA and V. R. DE CARVALHO, *Phytochemistry*, 1986, 25, 764.
26. B. DINDA and S. SAHA, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1986, 823.
27. K. YOSHIHIRA, M. TEZUKA, P. KANCHANAPEE, and S. NATORI, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Jpn.*, 1971, 19, 2271.
28. A. V. B. SANKARAM, A. S. RAO, and J. N. SHOOLERY, *Tetrahedron*, 1979, 35, 1777.
29. B. DINDA and S. SAHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, 28, 984.
30. G. M. K. B. GUNAHERATH, A. A. L. GUNATILAKA, and R. H. THOMSON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, 25, 4801.
31. A. MARSTON and K. HOSTETTSMANN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1984, 295, 526.
32. D. HADZI and N. SHEPPARD, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 911.
33. J. H. BOWIE, D. W. CAMERON, and D. H. WILLIAMS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 5094.
34. T. J. LILLIE, O. C. MUSGRAVE, and D. SKOYLES, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1976, 2155.
35. S. DE BURUAGA and J. VERDU, *Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1934, 32, 830.
36. L. F. FIESER and J. T. DUNN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 572.

37. R. H. THOMSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1237.
38. A. ICHIHARA, M. UBUKATA, and S. SAKAMURA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 44, 211.
39. G. WURM, U. GERES, and J. SCHMIDT, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1981, 314, 861.
40. I. KUBO, J. A. KLOCKE, T. MATSUMOTO, and T. KAMIKAWA in "IUPAC Pesticide Chemistry, Human Welfare and the Environment", ed. J. MIYAMOTO, Pergamon, Oxford, 1983, p. 169.
41. A. V. B. SANKARAM and G. S. SIDHU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 519.
42. H. LATTSCH, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1983, 299.
43. H. LATTSCH, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1984, 319.
44. H. LATTSCH, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1985, 2420.
45. S. BHARGAVA, M. AGIWAL, S. JAIN, R. T. PARDASANI, and P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, 70, 234.
46. R. DURAND and M. H. ZENK, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 3009.
47. H. V. SCHMID and M. H. ZENK, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 4151.
48. M. ALAM, K. K. S. DASAN, B. RUKMINI, and K. K. PURUSHOTHAMAN, *Ancient Sci. Life*, 1984, 4, 123.
49. M. ALAM, K. S. VASAN, B. RUKMINI, T. V. VARADARAJAN, R. B. RAO, and K. K. PURUSHOTHAMAN, *J. Res. Indian Med. Yoga Homeop.*, 1979, 14, 87.
50. D. S. ANTARKAR, A. B. VAIDYA, J. C. DOSHI, A. V. ATHAVALE, K. S. VINCHOO, M. R. NATEKAR, P. S. TATHEO, V. RAMESH, and N. KALE, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1980, 72, 588.
51. S. S. NANDA, A. SHARMA, and K. K. CHAKRABORTI, *Fitoterapia*, 1986, 57, 307.
52. O. G. DE LIMA, I. L. D'ALBUQUERQUE, G. M. MACIEL, and M. C. N. MACIEL, *Rev. Inst. Antibiot., Recife*, 1968, 8, 95.
53. M. KRISHNASWAMY and K. K. PURUSHOTHAMAN, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1980, 18, 876.
54. S. L. CRAFT, A. T. EVANS, and R. A. NEAL, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasitol.*, 1985, 79, 651.
55. B. B. SATHIA and S. LAL, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1933, 20, 777.
56. S. K. BHARGAVA, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1984, 22, 153.
57. G. SANTHAKUMARI, K. RATHINAM, and C. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1978, 16, 485.
58. R. P. SINGH, C. DEVAKUMAR, and S. DHINGRA, *Phytoparasitica*, 1988, 16, 225.
59. I. KUBO, M. TANIGUCHI, A. CHAPYA, and K. TSUJIMOTO, *Planta Medica Suppl.*, 1980, 185.
60. D. K. REED, M. JACOBSON, J. D. WARTHEN, E. C. UEBEL, N. J. TROMLEY, L. JURD, and B. FREEDMAN, *USDA Tech. Bull. (1641)*, 1981, 13.
61. G. T. GUJAR, *Fitoterapia*, 1990, 61, 387.
62. H. C. SHARMA, K. LEUSCHNER, A. V. B. SANKARAM, D. GUNASEKHAR, M. MANTHANDAMURTHI, K. BHASKARIAH, M. SUBRAMANYAM, and N. SULTANA in "Proc. 2nd. Neem Conference, Rauisholzhausen 1983", eds. H. SCHMUTTERER and K. R. S. ASCHER, and G. T. Z. ESCHBORN, 1983, p. 291.
63. G. T. GUJAR and K. N. MEHROTRA, *J. Appl. Ent.*, 1988, 105, 466.
64. I. KUBO, M. UCHIDA, and J. A. KLOCKE, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1983, 47, 911.
65. D. GHOSH, K. SOM, B. DINDA, and G. CHEL, *J. Adv. Zool.*, 1994, 15, 112.
66. A. MARSTON, J. D. MSONTHI, and K. HOSTETTMANN, *Planta Medica*, 1984, 50, 279.
67. A. MARSTON and K. HOSTETTMANN, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, 24, 639.
68. L. M. VAN DER VUIVER, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, 11, 3247.
69. X. L. QIAN and P. Z. ZHOU, *Hue Hsuch Hsuch Pao*, 1980, 38, 405 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, 93, 217916).
70. N. K. JOSHI, K. M. LATHIKA, A. BANERJI, and M. S. CHADHA, *Proc. Indian Nat. Sci. Acad.*, 1988, 854, 43.